

A Study of the Relationships Between Social Media Discussions and Company Stock Prices via Web Mining

*1. Chanthika PORNPITAKPAN; 2. Xindi WANG

*1. Corresponding author. Associate Professor in Management, Faculty of Business Administration, University of Macau, Avenida da Universidade, Taipa, Macau, China, e-mail: ynvynv@yahoo.com; ynvynv@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-1907-8540.

2. Officer, Balance of Payments Department, Guizhou Provincial Branch of the State Administration of Foreign Exchange, China, e-mail: 674926485@qq.com, ORCID: 0009-0006-5315-9076.

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Abstract

Purpose: Drawing on negativity biases and empirical evidence, this study infers that compared with positive publicity, negative publicity about a company is more memorable, more exciting to discuss about, and more conducive to building awareness of the company, which in turn has positive impacts on its sales and stock prices. It investigates relationships between social media discussions and stock prices using four Chinese companies.

Methods: Four publicly-traded Chinese companies including a residential developer, an e-commerce platform, a hot-pot restaurant chain, and an Internet service provider are examined. Through the event study method, the companies' historical stock prices and Weibo discussions are collected via web mining, and correlation analyses are used to examine the relationship between them.

Results: All the expected results are supported. Positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events, whereas no relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's positive events.

Conclusions: This study uses web mining to examine several publicly-traded Chinese companies and incorporates Weibo indicators. It links negativity biases with the impact on company stock prices in the short run. Public discussions about company negative events have more-favorable impacts on stock prices than do public discussions about company positive events, so managers should establish a professional public relations team to maneuver public sentiments.

Keywords: social media, Weibo platform, stock price, retailing companies, services companies, consumer behavior, marketing management, negativity bias

Valence of the news (ranging from negative to positive) may bring public attentions, so it is not surprising that some celebrities and companies try to increase their popularity even through negative publicity. In general, a corporate crisis is the perception of specific, unexpected, and unconventional events that threaten stakeholders' expectations, and such perceptions could seriously undermine an organization's operations or reputations and lead to negative outcomes (Coombs, 2007) and negative media coverage (Zavyalova et al., 2012). This has resulted in massive swings in the stock prices of some listed companies. For example, United Airlines' market capitalization value dropped by US\$1.4 billion overnight after its passenger expulsion appeared in social media sites in 2017 (Shen, 2017). Analyzing a longitudinal data set in the airline industry, Luo (2007) found that higher levels of current consumer complaints damaged companies' future idiosyncratic stock returns, which refer to the expected excessive company-specific cash flows in comparison with the average market portfolio returns of stock exchanges. Deng et al. (2017) found that negative microblog sentiments predicted lower stock returns in the hourly level but not in the daily level. Bellarosa (2019) found that when a scandal regarding a celebrity endorser was publicized, the company's stock return was negatively affected. Likewise, the findings of Spears (2021) showed that large global companies' valuation declined due to the negative publicity they faced. A protest of Tesla at the Shanghai Auto Show 2021 was found to deteriorate its stock performance while having an opposite effect on its competitor Nio even though Tesla undertook immediate remedial actions that were not positively accepted (Lim & Tan, 2022).

Nonetheless, some research did not find significant long-term negative effects of negative digital word-of-mouth events on company stock prices in the cases of Pepsi and United Airlines (Petrescu et al., 2018). Moreover, several incidents exist where companies gain the favor of consumers through positive actions. For example, a meta-analysis of 28 studies on the relationship between online reviews and sales found that star ratings in online reviews had a significantly positive effect on product sales (Li, Chen, & Zhang, 2020). These examples show that negative publicity and events tend to lead to negative outcomes, while positive publicity and events tend to bring positive outcomes. However, this study aims to show that contrary to conventional beliefs, company negative events may actually be associated with positive outcomes such as increased stock prices. The following section presents the objective of the study, literature review, and hypotheses.

Literature Review and Hypotheses

Social Media Influence and the Objective of the Study

The short-term market influences of social media discussions on the stock prices of listed companies have received a lot of public and academic attention in recent years (Antweiler & Frank, 2004). Because public discussions are tendentious and widespread, and because they can have social consequences (Liu et al., 2015), they have potential impacts on listed companies' short-term market reactions, and the capital market's sustainable growth. Besides, in today's world, social media have become increasingly accessible and important, leading many companies to use them as a marketing communications tool and a marketing channel, such as promoting and selling products through Facebook, Instagram, and X. This research focuses on the relationship between social media discussions and company share values or stock prices.

Sina Weibo (hereafter referred to as Weibo) is a Chinese information interaction network focusing on user relationships for exchanging and disseminating information. Information dissemination on Weibo is both explosive and superimposed. Users can login to the Weibo platform anytime anywhere to publish content, and there is no limit on the number of releases they can make. Information on Weibo attracts many users and stimulates their ability to express themselves because of the variety and innovation of its content editing, and

the information is typically forwarded by tens of thousands of users once it is published. As a result, Weibo plays an obvious role in corporate crisis communication as a time-sensitive information distribution tool.

In comparison to traditional media's lagging nature of information dissemination, Weibo's information dissemination has high fissionability and diffusion, and once the discussion of crisis events spreads, its effect has usually been concurrently generated with this information. Consequently, when a crisis arises, Weibo becomes an effective medium for communication and knowledge sharing, playing a key role in crisis communication and demonstrating business attitudes and social responsibility.

Research has shown that discussions on social media sites about business-related activities may have an effect on a company's equity values or stock prices (Luo, Zhang, & Duan, 2013). In particular, Luo et al. (2013) collected internet data and web traffic to examine the impact of social media on company equity value, which is calculated by multiplying a company's share price by its number of shares outstanding, and found that social media-based metrics (web blogs and consumer ratings) were significant indicators of company equity value. However, some studies did not find significant relationship between social media mentions and stock prices and between consumer sentiment ratio and stock prices of Dow Jones Industrial Average 30 companies (Rosa, 2022).

This research uses a case study and event study methodology to analyze the relationship between discussions about companies in social media and short-term stock prices of the companies. This will assist company executives and regulatory bodies in making informed business decisions and encouraging the healthy growth of the capital market. Specifically, it investigates the relationship between Weibo online discussions about four Chinese companies' crisis events and their stock prices. The companies consist of Country Garden (a residential developer), Pinduoduo (a third-party e-commerce platform), Haidilao (the largest hot-pot restaurant chain in China), and Tencent (a large integrated Internet service provider). To achieve manageable data analyses and to minimize variations in national, economic, and cultural environments, this study does not consider other foreign companies.

Factors That Affect Market Valuations of Companies

An analysis of quarterly data from companies in hundreds of industries over 20 years has found six important factors that influence market valuations of companies: weighted forecasts of growth in company revenue, weighted forecasts of growth in company margin, patterns of cash returned to shareholders, changes in the company's debt-to-equity ratio, the economic conditions in the company's industry, and market volatility in the geographic areas in which the industry's major companies compete (Trustman & Keely, 2022). With respect to the first factor, it is evident that anything that positively influences sales, such as service quality (Pornpitakpan & Han, 2013), people's mood (Pornpitakpan, Yuan, & Han, 2017), attitudes and purchase intentions toward the products (Pornpitakpan, Li, Sy-Changco, & Chen, 2025), advertising appeal (Pornpitakpan, 2003; Pornpitakpan & Green, 2007, 2010), advertisement size and repetition (Pornpitakpan, 2004a), perceived and actual product quality, customer loyalty, and awareness of the brand and the company, will also increase the company's revenues, valuations, and thus its stock prices.

Negativity Biases and Company Stock Prices

The negativity bias, also called the negativity effect, is a cognitive bias that, even when things are equally intense, neutral or positive things have a smaller impact on a person's psychological state and processes than do things that are more negative in nature, such as unfavorable thoughts, emotions, or social exchanges; and bruising or traumatic events (Rozin & Royzman, 2001). In other words, a very positive experience is typically less influential on an

individual's behavior and cognition than is a similarly emotional but negative experience. It is not surprising to see that after the content of news was controlled for, a news story was about 22% more likely to be included by media if it was negative (Niessner & So, 2018).

Numerous areas have been studied in relation to the negativity bias, including the development of first impressions and general judgments, attention, learning, as well as decision-making and risk assessment. For example, a comparison of the Twitter (renamed as X in July 2023) sentiment indexes' movements with the daily closing stock price of 24 large publicly-traded companies in the world revealed that the intensity with which negative news influenced stock prices was greater than that of positive news (Mendoza-Urdiales et al., 2022). Herrando et al.'s (2022) neuroscience experiment using physiological analyses through skin conductance response found that the emotional arousal of the observers (i.e., readers of online consumer reviews) aligned with that of the observed (i.e., writers of online consumer reviews). The neural analyses through electroencephalography showed that negative reviews activated arousal and pleasure in the observers, whereas positive reviews were associated with arousal deactivation and displeasure. Aggarwal et al. (2012) found that negative posts could exponentially increase the readership of employee blogs. Ekdahl (2015) discovered that negative press releases were associated with positive subsequent abnormal returns for middle-sized companies in the New York Stock Exchange. Noteworthy, it was found that consumer interest in a brand actually increased during a negative digital word-of-mouth campaign (Petrescu et al., 2018). Accordingly, it may be inferred that compared with positive publicity/news, negative publicity/news about a company is more memorable, more exciting and enjoyable to discuss about, and more conducive to building awareness of the company, and such company awareness, in turn, has positive impacts on sales and thus the company's valuation and stock prices.

In line with the above tenet, negative publicity/news can bring about positive effects, whereas positive publicity/news can lead to negative outcomes. For instance, Berger, Sorensen, and Rasmussen (2010) collected sales and reviews of 244 books published during 2001–2003 and found that negative publicity can increase book sales by raising public awareness. In contrast, Kovács and Sharkey (2014) compared Goodreads.com reviews of books that won or were shortlisted for prestigious book awards between 2007 and 2011 by 64 reader reviews of English-language books and found that positive publicity indeed led to lower ratings for the books having won awards and decreased book sales. Following the above rationales, inferences, and empirical findings, the following results are expected:

Hypothesis 1: Positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events.

Furthermore, it was found that in the financial services context, negative sentiments correlated with companies' future stock prices whereas the number of tweets and the positive sentiment of tweets did not correlate with stock prices (He et al., 2016). Operationalizing social media net sentiment as the result of the total percentage of positive posts less the percentage of negative posts, Widmar et al. (2020) found weak evidence of relationships between stock price performance and net sentiment for Disney World. These empirical results lead to the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: No relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's positive events.

The next section explains the methods of the study.

Methods

Selection of Cases for the Research

Because the aim of this research is to examine stock prices of listed companies, representative events and companies from the recent years were chosen first, followed by the

exclusion of many unlisted companies and companies that were closed on the day of the event. Four companies remain: two did not handle the crisis event properly (i.e., they had negative crisis management, leading to primarily negative public discussions about the company and thus hereafter referred to as negative events), whereas the other two handled the crisis properly (i.e., they had positive crisis management, leading to primarily positive public discussions about the company and thus hereafter referred to as positive events). Appendix 1 displays brief descriptions of the four cases.

Definition of the Event Date, the Event Period, the Estimated Period, and the Variables

This section explains the terms used in the event study of this research. The **event date** refers to the date on which a crisis involving a listed company is first addressed by the public on social media sites; for example, the event date of Country Garden according to Appendix 1 is April 16, 2019. The **event period** is defined as the period 10 business days for trading stocks before and after the event date plus the event date itself; for example, in this case the event period will be April 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, **16 (event date)**, 17, 18, 23, 24, 25, 26, 29, 30, May 2, and May 3, 2019. The **estimated period of the event** refers to three calendar months before the event period; for example, in this case the estimated period of the event is January 1 to March 31, 2019. Given the various real-world variables that can affect stock prices, the range of the event duration chosen cannot be too broad for the empirical findings to be substantially relevant. In addition, the estimated period and the event period must be independent of each other.

Table 1 shows the definitions of the variables in this research.

Table 1
Definitions of Variables

Variable Name	Definition
Daily stock closing prices	The closing price of company stocks for each day during the specified period.
Daily number of original posts on Weibo about the company	Number of original posts on Weibo about the company updated every day with the company's name as a keyword.

Acquisition and Processing of Daily Stock Trading Data

This research used Pandas_datareader, a Python application for remotely obtaining financial data that allows users to access data from a variety of companies and organizations, including Yahoo Finance, Google Finance, the World Bank, and others. It primarily automates the entire processing of financial data such as market prices, from data collection to cleaning, processing, and storage. Python was used to write and execute the system. The daily stock prices for the four stocks needed in this study were mostly obtained from the Yahoo Finance website via the Pandas_datareader package's get data Yahoo module for historical quotes. This module gathers historical market data from Datareader, including useful details like the stock's opening price, closing price, current day's high, current day's low, and volume for the stated period.

To use these data, one must submit a request to the server's application programming interface (API) with the requested stock code and the period corresponding to the desired stock's history data, and the server will return all of the data for that stock for the specified period. Because of the advantages of the Python Pandas package in quantitative financial

analysis, Pandas was used for the majority of the data formats in this research. In addition, to satisfy the needs of each analysis and to save the data and analysis results more conveniently, Excel was used to store the financial data locally.

Acquisition and Processing of Weibo Data

This study collected data about the four companies' discussions on the Weibo website using a public crawler system on GitHub. The crawler code primarily analyzed the interface on the Weibo website using Chrome, obtained the interface parameters, used the requests library to simulate requests, included cookies, and then saved the crawled data in a CSV file. It firstly searched for Weibo using company name keywords and then crawled the data for the event span of 21 days. The obtained fields were user nickname, Weibo ID, post time, Weibo content, and whether it was an original Weibo post. The posting time and whether the Weibo post was original were the fields used in this research to count the number of discussions regarding the company's original Weibo posts for each day of the event period.

Results

Descriptive Statistics of the Stocks

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of the stock prices of the four companies for the combined estimated period and event period.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Stocks of the Four Companies for the Combined Estimated Period and Event Period

Company	Stock Price	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.
Country Garden (negative event, price in HKD)	High	71	9.7500	13.5600	11.6577	1.0856
	Low	71	9.3400	13.1800	11.2482	1.0801
	Open	71	9.4500	13.3200	11.4497	1.0769
	Close	71	9.4400	13.2800	11.4611	1.0709
	AdjClose	71	8.3767	11.7842	10.1702	0.9503
Pinduoduo (negative event, price in USD)	High	73	72.2900	187.7000	132.3066	34.7916
	Low	73	69.8900	176.5000	124.6207	32.2625
	Open	73	72.0000	184.3700	128.1981	33.8511
	Close	73	72.0700	187.2000	128.8004	33.5985
	AdjClose	73	72.0700	187.2000	128.8004	33.5985
Haidilao (positive event, price in HKD)	High	74	29.3000	35.9000	32.7007	1.6942
	Low	74	27.4500	35.2500	31.1507	1.8585
	Open	74	28.9500	35.8000	31.9635	1.7921
	Close	74	28.2500	35.7000	31.9047	1.8499
	AdjClose	74	28.1369	35.5570	31.7769	1.8425
Tencent (positive event, price in HKD)	High	72	376.4000	564.0000	443.7444	48.8937
	Low	72	369.6000	546.0000	432.8444	45.7356
	Open	72	370.0000	549.0000	437.8014	45.6462
	Close	72	374.4000	563.0000	439.0236	47.6387
	AdjClose	72	373.3566	563.0000	438.5556	47.9920

Note. Descriptive statistics were analyzed for stock data for the combined estimated period and event period. Because of the different number of days of stock suspensions in the estimated period, the sample volume ranges from 71 to 74.

Relationships Between Stock Prices and Online Discussions

To test the hypotheses, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. The data file for the negative events consists of, among others, the daily stock closing price of Country Garden for 21 days, followed by that of Pinduoduo for 21 days in one column, and the corresponding daily number of original posts on Weibo about the company of Country Garden for 21 days, followed by that of Pinduoduo for 21 days in another column. The correlation analysis reveals that for negative events, the daily stock closing prices during the event period correlated positively with the daily number of original posts on Weibo about the company, $r = .459$, $p = .001$, supporting Hypothesis 1 that positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events.

In the same manner, the data file for the positive events consists of, among others, the daily stock closing price of Haidilao for 21 days, followed by that of Tencent for 21 days in one column, and the corresponding daily number of original posts on Weibo about the company of Haidilao for 21 days, followed by that of Tencent for 21 days in another column. The correlation analysis reveals that for positive events, the daily stock closing price during the event period did not significantly correlate with the daily number of original posts on Weibo about the company, $r = .25$, $p = .055$, supporting Hypothesis 2 that no relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's positive events.

Discussion

In this section, some limitations of the study and future research suggestions are presented first, followed by discussion of the research and its contributions and implications.

Limitations and Future Research Suggestions

Every research study, regardless of the budgets and time of the researchers, has limited scopes of investigations and objectives. Likewise, several limitations of this study are presented here to suggest what future research may do further. First, the focus of the study is short-term effects of company-specific online discussions on the Weibo platform on the stock prices of four large Chinese companies. Therefore, future studies may include a greater number of companies in China and other countries, especially countries that vastly differ from China culturally such as the USA and Europe, to achieve larger sample sizes, to obtain more data, and to compare the results between countries.

Second, this study purposely chooses companies from different industries to broaden the analysis and to avoid the potential criticism that the results may only be applicable to a particular company or to a particular industry. However, the diverse events might cause investors' reactions within different length of time. The inconsistent comparison base might make it rather hard to come up with objective results and might encounter the generalization problems. To address this issue, future research may adopt another approach by using the same company with different types of events (happened in different time) or the same type of event with different companies in the same industry. Additional ideas for future research include studying the effects of online discussions on stock prices in positive events and negative events of a single company through time to minimize extraneous factors. Effects over a longer time span may also be examined. It should be taken note that if these approaches are adopted, challenges might be raised with respect to the "overfitting" issues, industry-specific or even company-specific applicability and validity, and too narrow scope of comparisons.

Third, because this study uses correlation analysis, which does not permit strong causality conclusions, future research may use experiments with proper control of extraneous variables to investigate the impact of valence of word of mouth or online discussions on

consumers' intentions to sell company stocks and anticipated stock prices. In particular, research has found that consumers' circadian arousal and time of day influence consumer attitudes and behaviors (Gullo et al., 2019; Pornpitakpan, 2004b). Future studies should therefore investigate the influence of time of day and investors' morningness–eveningness (see Caci et al., 2005; Pornpitakpan, 1998, 2000; and Pornpitakpan, Yue, & Fu, 2025 for the validation of morningness–eveningness measures on people from several countries such as Thailand and China) on attitudes toward the company and purchase intentions toward the company stocks. Furthermore, source credibility has been an important variable in numerous fields of research for decades (see review regarding source credibility by Pornpitakpan, 2004c), and it is closely related to company reputation. Therefore, future experimental studies may manipulate company reputation and credibility via the use of scenarios to see its impact on investors' attitudes toward the company and purchase intentions toward the company stocks. Additionally, future experimental studies may manipulate the physical attractiveness of the people who post comments online (see review regarding source attractiveness by Pornpitakpan, Li, & Fu, 2017) to see its influence on investors' attitudes toward the company and purchase intentions toward the company stocks.

Fourth, this study examines positive events that are due to positive crisis management of the company and negative events that arise from improper crisis management of the company. Future research may study positive events that are the company's admirable behaviors, such as good corporate social responsibility actions and cause-marketing campaigns. Similarly, future research may investigate negative events that are the company's bad behaviors, such as committing illegal and unethical business practices, using controversial advertisements, and discrimination against certain groups of people.

Next, future research can investigate the effect of negative events/news that are detrimental to the company's financial status on their stock prices, for example, the company's bankruptcy filing and heavy fines and penalties imposed by the government or the courts. These kinds of negative events/news may hardly be associated with increased stock prices but if they are, it would be very interesting to find out the underlying mechanisms.

Finally, the use of case study and event study approach does not allow conclusions of causal relationships and profound generalization of results. However, readers may want to take note that the aim of this study is to utilize big data gathered from social media, not to ascertain causal relationships, which would require the use of experimental research that also has its own limitations such as unreal and tightly controlled laboratory settings and thus having limited generalizability to real-world settings. If only causal/experimental research can be published in reputable academic journals, then we will not see other kinds of studies such as conceptual studies, qualitative studies, and studies utilizing secondary data and big data being published in high-ranked journals. However, the reality is just the opposite—we can see various kinds of studies, whether causal or non-causal, in high-ranked academic journals.

Discussion of the Study

This research first introduces four events involving four publicly traded companies on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange or the Nasdaq Stock Exchange, determines the date of the events, and then uses web mining and correlation analysis to examine empirically the relationship between social media discussions and stock prices of the four companies, namely Country Garden, Pinduoduo, Haidilao, and Tencent. Country Garden and Pinduoduo did not handle their crisis events properly (i.e., they had negative crisis management, leading to primarily negative public discussions about the company and thus referred to as negative events), whereas Haidilao and Tencent handled their crisis events properly (i.e., they had positive crisis management, leading to primarily positive public discussions about the company and thus referred to as positive events). All the expected results derived from

negativity biases and relevant empirical findings are supported by the data as elaborated below.

First, significant positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events. In other words, higher numbers of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events are associated with higher stock prices. Second, no significant relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's positive events. This finding is consistent with previous research suggesting that no matter the publicity is positive or negative, the company can increase its visibility by such publicity, meaning negative publicity could exert a positive effect by increasing a company's visibility to the public (Berger et al., 2010). When bad things happen, investors assume that the company's flaws have been exposed and thus what is left should be good. Investors, on the other hand, may believe that favorable events for the company are indicative of what it should be doing, so they may not place as much emphasis on positive events.

Contributions and Implications of the Research

Social media has long been used as a tool for marketing communications and product selling and distribution, but the impact of social media discussions on stock prices is little known in this context. The relationship between social media valence/sentiment for a specific entity and a related indicator such as fluctuations in its stock prices is an important and growing area of research (Schweidel & Moe, 2014; Tirunillai & Tellis, 2012). Using big data analysis, this study clearly contributes to this field of investigation.

The results of this study show that positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events, a finding contrary to intuitions, conventional beliefs, and some research findings but indeed consistent with this study's hypothesis derived from negativity biases and some previous empirical evidence. In other words, public discussions about company negative events have more-favorable impacts on a company's short-term stock prices than do public discussions about company positive events, possibly because negative publicity makes people remember and aware of the companies more than does positive publicity, and such company awareness in turn has positive impacts on its sales and thus the company valuation and stock prices.

Theoretically, this research has several contributions/implications. First and foremost, it presents a novel research approach in empirically studying the relationship between online discussions on social media platforms and company stock prices. Previous studies typically investigate the effects of performances, brand image, and reputation of publicly traded companies on their stock prices. Second, this study examines several cases whereas previous studies are mostly single-case analyses, with only a few involving multiple cases. Third, this study extends the previously utilized variable of public conversations to incorporate Weibo indicators (Weibo original posts) to assess their impacts on short-term market reactions. In this way, it compares positive and negative events and lays the groundwork for future research to determine the similarities and differences between positive and negative online discussion contents that influence stock prices.

Several practical implications can be drawn from this study's finding that social media discussions relate to short-term stock prices of listed companies. First, company managers should be aware of the power of social media and establish a professional social-media public relations team to maneuver public sentiments and to prevent the company's stock prices from fluctuating significantly when a crisis occurs.

Second, in general, public reactions to listed companies' negative events are stronger than public reactions to positive events. As a result, when a company crisis occurs, in order to avoid unfavorable legal consequences and to increase the public's goodwill toward the company and thus maintaining the stability of the company's stock prices, managers and

public relations teams should adopt proper solutions that do not evade responsibilities or do not lie to the stakeholders and the public.

Third, managers of highly reputable companies should be aware that such a high reputation may increase the stakeholders' strictness. Therefore, they should pay more attention to public discussions on social platforms and launch public relations measures that correspond to the topics and events discussed by the public to take care of people's interests and emotions.

Finally, managers should pay attention to other performance indicators of the company apart from stock prices. These include sales, market shares, profits, company and brand images, company and brand awareness, brand loyalty, social and ethical responsibility, and so on. Even though this study finds that positive relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's negative events, and that no relationships exist between stock prices and quantities of original posts on Weibo about the company's positive events, companies should definitely not try to increase public discussions about the company by deliberately conducting bad things—a popular strategy used by many celebrities nowadays—because these are unethical/immoral, may invite government investigation/interference, may generate consumer boycott and animosity toward the company, and may have negative impacts on the company's operations and goodwill in the long run.

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Appendix 1

Descriptions of the Selected Cases and Events

Company Name and Characteristics	Type and Date of the Event	Brief Descriptions of the Event
<p>Country Garden. Stock Code: HK02007. It is China's largest new urbanization residential developer, listed on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange in 2007.</p>	<p>Negative, 2019-04-16</p>	<p>On April 16, 2019, a Weibo user posted that part of the classrooms of the new kindergarten located next to the wall collapsed during the demolition of the Cinnamon Park-Qindu Mansion project in Qindu District, Xianyang City, due to improper demolition. Accidents have become more common in Country Garden projects since 2018. Country Garden has adopted an arrogant and dismissive attitude toward quality concerns, workers, and the protection of consumers' lives, making it impossible to quell public outrage. Following this incident, many netizens slammed Country Garden as a hastily designed project, and the company's credibility and word of mouth have plummeted.</p>
<p>Pinduoduo. Stock Code: PDD. It is a mainstream Chinese third-party e-commerce platform focusing on C2M group shopping, listed on the Nasdaq Stock Exchange in 2018.</p>	<p>Negative, 2021-01-04</p>	<p>A female Pinduoduo employee collapsed on her way home from work at 01:30 on December 29, 2020 and died after being resuscitated. The company's official response to the news was a comment posted by the company's verified account on Zhihu, which gave the public the impression that the company had no regret. On January 4, 2021, the incident became a hot search on Weibo, capturing the attention of the entire network, and the outrage of public opinions outweighed the woman's sudden death. Pinduoduo debunked the reports at 19:00 on January 4, 2021. Thousands of netizens and Zhihu's official accounts quickly verified that the comment was indeed issued by a Pinduoduo official and then deleted on its own. Covering up an issue with a lie is an incredibly poor decision. It has been established that the discovery of the lie is an unavoidable outcome, and that the collapse of confidence occurs only a short time after the lie is discovered. Pinduoduo not only failed to regain its image but also sparked a new round of outrage among netizens because of this incident.</p>
<p>Haidilao. Stock Code: HK06862. It is the largest hot pot chain in China, listed on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange in 2018.</p>	<p>Positive, 2020-04-07</p>	<p>The Haidilao price increase incident, which occurred on April 7, 2020, ignited a large number of netizens' discussions on Weibo and was constantly on Weibo hot search. On April 10, the official Weibo site of Haidilao hotpot released an apology note, claiming that the prices of dishes in stores across the country would be restored to the level that existed before the stores closed on January 26, 2021. In this apology letter, Haidilao stated that the company's management made a mistake, causing</p>

Company Name and Characteristics	Type and Date of the Event	Brief Descriptions of the Event
<p>Tencent. Stock Code: HK00700. It is one of the largest integrated Internet service providers in China and one of the largest Internet companies serving the largest number of users in China, listed on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange in 2004.</p>	<p>Positive, 2020-06-30</p>	<p>harm to customers' interests. In order to protect customers' interests, the company chose to restore rates, giving consumers the impression that Haidilao is still the service leader. Since the apology is genuine, many customers are able to buy, accept the letter of apology, and continue to spend. The visibility of Haidilao has risen drastically because of this occurrence.</p> <p>Tencent sued Lao Ganma in late June 2020, alleging that Lao Ganma owed it 16.24 million RMB in advertisement payments, and asked the court to freeze 16.24 million RMB in assets held by Lao Ganma. However, Lao Ganma stated on June 30, 2020 that there was no commercial cooperation with Tencent and reported the issue to the public security authorities.</p> <p>The Tencent Weibo service was introduced on June 30, 2020, with the expression "It's hard to say" to describe the process of being cheated, which exacerbated the aggravation of an individual being cheated, leading the public to empathize and sympathize with the company, and Tencent was instantly turned into a vulnerable person who had been cheated. Furthermore, Tencent's official response claimed that they would reward the netizens who provided clues with Lao Ganma's products, which showed the sincerity of Tencent's apology. The organization not only addressed the humiliation but also reclaimed the sympathy and goodwill of netizens, thanks to some "self-deprecating" crisis management.</p>

Note. Investors around the world can buy stocks traded in the Hong Kong Stock Exchange and the Nasdaq Stock Exchange.